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THE CURRENT ROLE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE ORGANIZATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In this article you can learn about the role of foreign languages in the education policy of Uzbekistan, the growing need for a language-based society and the step-by-step practice of this process, the ongoing reforms (decisions, innovations, changes).

Keywords: Attention to language, the role of foreign languages in the history of Uzbekistan, Resolution No. 1875 PQ, Resolution No. 5117 PQ, IELTS, CEFR, PISA, PIRLS and their impact on the development of the educational process, foreign educational institutions, schools and foreign languages in Uzbekistan.

In independent Uzbekistan, education in public schools is conducted in 7 languages it is well known that national policy is lacking in world experience. (S.Shermuhammedov academician)

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, as in all spheres of society, many new reforms have been implemented in the field of education over the past 10 years. Among them is the growing demand for teaching foreign languages in the field of education, as well as the adoption of new decisions aimed at improving the science of foreign languages, the work carried out on the basis of decisions - all based on modern standards of the younger generation. , it was the most precious opportunity created for them to be educated. The role of language is invaluable in the prosperity of any

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nation as a nation. the need to organize foreign languages has risen to the level of politics. In 1981-1987, 72% of scientific works prepared at the Institute of History of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan were published in Russian, 20% in foreign languages and 8% in Uzbek. Today, it continues to improve and meet the requirements of the times. In addition, the unique works created by our great figures are still preserved in various countries around the world. In particular: Mirzo Ulugbek's "History of the Four Nations" in libraries of England, India, USA; Chalgani's Arithmetic of the Nine at Princeton University; The original of Al-Khwarizmi's Al-Jabr val muqabala is kept in the Oxford Library. In order to enjoy such masterpieces, it is necessary to organize a foreign language.

Taking into account the above issues, on the initiative of the first President of our country IA Karimov in 2012, teaching foreign languages on the basis of Resolution No. 1875PQ made a significant contribution to the introduction of new ideas and teaching methods in education. In particular, students have been taught in schools since the 1st grade, 1 day a week of teacher exchange days has been organized as ICT-based training courses, computer technology and multimedia have been used to a high degree, various demonstration tools to give educational institutions a new enthusiasm for lessons on the state budget. as well as methodological assistance. Textbooks have been updated, various international competitions, science Olympiads, English proficiency tests (IELTS / CEFR / TESOL) have been organized. All this has strengthened the love for language in the minds and imaginations of young students, educators. Over time, the world has changed, people's worldviews have expanded, the educational potential of young

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people has increased, time has improved. As a result, the decision was amended.

On May 19, 2021, a new resolution of the 2nd President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.MIRZIYOEV No. PP-5117 "On measures to bring the organization of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level" was approved and entered into force. : "Introduction of an uninterrupted chain of education on the principle of" kindergarten-school-higher education institution-enterprise ".

Proof of this decision is the holding of online and offline Olympiads in foreign languages in our country, several competitions for foreign language teachers, the increase to the extent that it can be published; the inclusion of foreign language exams in almost all areas of higher education, the granting of national and international benefits based on the criteria of foreign language proficiency, the publication of works expressing our national pride and pride not only in our native language but also in foreign languages a wide range of opportunities was created, such as demonstration.

In addition, knowledge testing programs such as PISA and PIRLS have become widespread at the school level. It is their extension that is also in English. Namely: PISA - Program for International Student Assessment is a worldwide study conducted by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in member and non-member countries. This is an international assessment program aimed at assessing the literacy of 15-year-old students in reading, mathematics and natural sciences. Therefore, on July 8, 2020, the OECD

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(Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development) held a rally to organize the PISA survey. Since then, trainings and tests on this program have been conducted in educational institutions of the country.

PIRLS - Progress in International Reading Literacy Study. The study, which aims to develop students' reading skills in scientific, historical, geographical, social and other forms of information texts, was also initially tested at Boston University in the United States and has conducted several studies to date. For example: Between 2001 and 2016, it was implemented among 4th graders from a total of 20 countries. Summarizing the results achieved, the PIRLS program website (pirls2016.org) was launched in 2016 to develop leak literacy at home or outside of school. For the first time in Uzbekistan, international participation in this research was launched in 2021.

Another world-class appraisal program is STEAM !!! This direction is at least a long-awaited and modern study, which, like the above, came from foreign education. S - science, T - technology, E - engineering, A - art, M - math (mathematics), based on the improvement of specific sciences and robotics new educational program. This year, seminars and trainings in this area have been organized in recent years, many branches of foreign universities have started operating in our country. Education at these universities is conducted in English and Russian. This is another striking example of both the emphasis on language and the development of education. Many of our young people have now been educated and are bringing knowledge to the universities I want to cite below. It is gratifying that over the next year, foreign students are coming to our country to study.

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Branches of foreign universities operating in our country:

1. Westminster International University in Tashkent (WIUT) - A branch of Westminster University in the United Kingdom has been teaching in Tashkent since 2002. The university focuses on teaching economics. Here has the following undergraduate majors:

- * Business Administration;
- * Commercial Law;
- * Economics With Finance;
- * Business Information System;

2. Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent - The Polytechnic University of Turin, Italy has been operating in Uzbekistan since 2009. This university focuses on disciplines such as automotive, mechanical engineering. List of undergraduate majors:

- * Mechanical Engineering;
- * Industrial and Civil Engineering and Architecture;
- * Information Technologies and Programming in Industry (Computer Engineering);

3. YEOJU Technical Institute in Tashkent is a branch of the Korean Institute of Architecture, Construction, Marketing and Economics. Started work in 2018.

Directions:

- * Architecture and Urban design;
- * Civil engineering;
- * Renewable energy;

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* Tourism;

* International marketing;

4. MDIS (Management Development Institute of Singapore) in Tashkent - Singapore Institute of Management Development, based on finance, business and marketing, has been operating in our country since 2007. Available directions:

* Banking and Finance;

* Industrial management;

* International Hospitality and Tourism Management;

* Applied Travel, Tourism and Hospitality Management;

5. Bucheon University in Tashkent - The branch of Bucheon University in Korea has been teaching Primary Education, Architecture and Korean in Tashkent since 2018. Areas:

* Department of preschool education (3 + 1);

* Department of architecture (3 + 1);

* Department of Korean language and business administration (2 + 2);

6. SHARDA University Uzbekistan is a new University in Uzbekistan, which began its activities in 2020 and includes the following areas:

* Computer Science and Engineering;

* CSE with specialization in Cyber Security and Forensic;

* CSE with specialization in AI and Machine learning;

* BBA - Human resource Management;

* BBA - Entrepreneurship;

7. British Management University - This University is new, currently enrolled for the 2020-2021 academic year. There are bachelor's and master's degrees:

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- * Banking and Finance;
- * Finance and Investments;
- * International Accounting;
- * Project management;
- * International logistics and trade and etc.

"New Uzbekistan begins with the school threshold, the system of education and upbringing," said President Mirziyoyev. We have launched another new project for the children, teachers and students of this country – PRESIDENTIAL SCHOOLS !!!

Aims and objectives of the Presidential Schools: These schools are specialized state general education institutions whose activities are aimed at identifying and educating gifted children to train highly qualified specialists.

It is gradually being organized in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent on the basis of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 20, 2019 PQ-4199 "On measures to establish presidential schools." It was opened in 2019 in Tashkent, Khiva, Nukus and Namangan. The goal is to prepare future leaders and students of the nation who will win international Olympiads and competitions and enter the best universities in the world. Training leaders who can compete on the world stage. ” The entrance exams for schools consist of 2 stages, and students aged 10-11 (5th grade) who have achieved good results in both stages are admitted to the school on a grant basis without any fees. Here we have also considered the reasons for the growing interest in learning foreign languages in the territory of Uzbekistan. It is our duty to make full use of the total opportunities created. we need to teach or acquire

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knowledge in sync with new ideas and methods. It is our duty to radically reform the decisions made in each of the educational decisions, to show practical evidence. Because the representatives of all spheres of education are equally responsible for the future of the young generation, which is the future of the country, and its role in the future society. It is safe to say that teaching Uzbek children in English as well as their mother tongue has become one of the main principles of today's educators. teacher - unifier, teacher - great motivator !!! Let's be loyal to our profession and dedicated to education!

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